

CULTURAL CONTEXT AND LITERARY TRANSLATION WORDS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the difficulties of translation from one language to another and the skill of the translator in delivering the meaning of the text to the reader. With the development of the translation training, the interests of identifying and preventing problems associated with translation has also increased.

The cultural context is also constantly changing with changes in time and space, and its dynamics must be addressed by the internal range of translation. Therefore, in the process of translating one language into another language, especially in literary translation, translators must make an internal intermediate compensation between the cultural context and the translation, i.e. compensate with the expansion of the connotation of the two languages and cultures. The problems arising from the point of view of the inherent cultural differences between the two languages should be translated to the letter, to the letter and to the maximum of elegance.

Key words: Artistic translation; cultural context; connotation; cultural difference; semantic migration

Introduction

Translation is the process of changing internal and external meanings from one language to another, which requires not only a deep understanding of the source (source language) and target language (target language), but also the mastery of both. Alienation of language corresponds to transformation. Mr. Yang Fu, a famous Chinese translator, said, "The three difficulties in translation are reliable and elegant." The way to solve the complex problems of translation is also a process that many translation researchers are constantly innovating in the research process. Translation is the link of intercultural communication. Translation and culture, especially the cultural context, are closely related and inseparable. Therefore, translation should be a product integrated with the cultural context.

1. Cultural context and internal gap compensation in translation

From the point of view of scientists, culture is "a complex body that includes knowledge, beliefs, art, ethics, law, customs and other skills and habits acquired in society". In the course of human social and historical practice, the cultural context changes with the evolution of culture, and "the main trend of cultural evolution is convergence, that is, with the development of culture, different cultures tend to merge more and more; as long as culture exists, it is a cultural process. The convergence is infinite. Cultural context is the part most affected by the convergence of cultural evolution, so it plays a decisive role in translation, especially in the translation of words in literary translation. Cultural context and translation ultimately require internal compensation to be resolved. The famous English social anthropologist Malinowski divided the context into three categories, namely: discourse

context, situational context, and cultural context. Among them, the definition of cultural context has several different interpretations. One refers to the social and cultural background related to oral communication, and the other refers to the cognitive environment of people in a specific culture, which includes language. Environment, concrete context, and cognitive context. Each of these links is closely related to language. Language is a carrier of culture and an inseparable organic part of culture.

The famous American sinologist Professor Lee Dasan (John Dini) said in his work "Biculturalis and Translation": "Every language gets its life and nourishment from culture, so we only need to know how to translate the language." We can't ignore it. To become another language, we must strive to express the ways of thinking and expressing feelings of the two cultures." The language gap caused by different cultural backgrounds requires an internal intermediate solution, and the analysis of the cultural context is the first and most important solution. Due to the subjectivity and dynamics of the context of translation, the construction of the cultural context cannot be completed at once, but is an endless process of dialogue, and the specific scope of translation is given to its dialogic character.

The cultural context is also constantly changing with changes in time and space, and its dynamics must be addressed by the internal range of translation. Therefore, in the process of translating one language into another language, especially in literary translation, translators must make an internal intermediate compensation between the cultural context and the translation, i.e. compensate with the expansion of connotations of the two languages and cultures. The problems arising from the point of view of the inherent cultural differences between the two languages should be translated to the letter, to the letter and to the maximum of elegance. The understanding of the cultural context is limited by the translator and is influenced by the translator's own interests, needs, knowledge, experience, literary and artistic achievements, values and personal beliefs, so it can be solved within the framework of subjectivity. That is, the translator must understand the transfer relationship between the cultural context and the translation of literary words.

2. The transfer relationship between the cultural context and the translation of literary words

Some scientifics have stated that "language is a direct event of thinking", "especially vocabulary that most sensitively reflects changes in social life and social thinking, as well as a cultural label of an individual or social group." How to understand the real-life reflection of vocabulary, that is, how to understand the connotation of the cultural context. The transfer relationship between the cultural context and the translation is undoubtedly manifested in the use of words, especially in the translation of words in literary translation.

The deep cultural connotations contained in words cannot be conveyed without a deep understanding of the culture and its context. The text translated into another language looks blurry and unclear, and even the words do not make sense.

Differential shift in connotation

Professor Cao Jinghua said in a lecture to the teachers and students of Peking University: "It is difficult to set standards for literary translation, which in a sense is the re-creation of literature and art." The art of language is persuading people by using images instead of persuading them with logical arguments. Translators should not only fully introduce the meaning of the original text to the readers so that it will have the same understanding as the native readers. possible aim for a language style that is clear and simple, but also preserves

the beauty of the original work. Literary translation is the second processing of the author's work in a literary work. Mr. Mao Dun said about translation: "A good translator reads foreign words on the one hand, and on the other hand thinks and imagines in his own language, and conveys the content and style of the original work." This requires the translator to be able to identify the transfer of the inner meaning of the words affected by the context. If we take the names of characters in literary works as an example, the writers in Chinese and foreign works are the same. Most of the roles played in the works were given high hopes, and the characters were given deep meaning. The names of the characters often vividly express the author's creative motive, the social phenomenon and essence reflected in the work, and can reflect his own life. It reveals the creator's point of view and even the character and fate of the characters. Due to the wide acceptance of the works, the inner meaning of the names in the works of the characters has also changed. Cinderella is the main character of fairy tales loved by children all over the world. She is a beautiful girl who is driven by her stepmother and two sisters. Prince's lover. Cinderella is included in the current English vocabulary. And Longman dictionary is a modern dictionary. The English language interprets Cinderella as "an undead person (something) worthy of attention or respect." Another example is Hamlet, the main character of one of Shakespeare's most famous tragedies, the Danish prince who is depressed because of his father's murder. His uncle kills his father, usurps the throne and marries Hamlet's mother. Hamlet wants to avenge his father, but his introversion and caution make him hesitate. The New English Dictionary means "a person who thinks but is not decisive," leaving Hamlet without the Prince of Denmark, which means "removing the main thing." PeterPan refers to innocent adults who have not grown up; James Bond and his codename 007 have become synonymous with supernatural powers; A brave man"; Eugenie Grandet is an extremely stingy person. "Lin Daiyu" described by Chinese writers is synonymous with sentimental women; "Zhang Fei" is a careless person; "Cao Cao" is a traitor; a metaphor is pinchable and means those who has great wisdom. There is an old saying: "Three leaders are worth one Zhuge Li Ang", which translates to "The minds of three leaders combined are equal to that of Grandmaster Zhuge Li Ang." When translating this sentence, it is necessary to add explanatory content to it. Changing the connotation of the cultural background to allow the user of another language to understand the underlying meaning. A character's name cannot be lost in translation. The inner meaning is related to transmission.

Transfer of semantics in words

The transfer relationship between the cultural context and the translation of literary words is also reflected in the semantic transfer of words. In the mother tongue, that is, in the original language, the original pragmatic meaning of some words underwent semantic changes in different contextual conditions. Such changes cannot be properly translated into the target language without a deep understanding of the culture of the original language. Taking English and Chinese translation as an example, there are many colorful words that represent different meanings. In Chinese, "Huangmaoyatou" means "little stupid girl", and "yellow film" is "blue films". "Idiot" means "idiot" and "pink eye" means "green eye". The original meaning of green is the symbol of life and life. In Chinese, "wearing a hat" has expanded its meaning to mean "someone's wife has an affair with others", so "someone wears a green hat". cannot be literally translated into "to wear a green hat." It can be translated into "to be a cuck old" to transfer the semantics of the original context to the target language context.

"Nianmayue" does not actually translate to "year of the monkey or month of the horse", but according to Chinese custom, it translates to "knows when". It is mainly caused by endocrine abnormality and heavy exercise. For example, Sha Ting's "The Tale of the Beast in the Hood" says: "Or be patient and get out of this dead end so as not to cancel the acting plan." "Patiently break the dead lock to avoid mistakes in the game. Also words like 'paper tiger', lose face, etc. vividly express the strong cultural characteristics of the source language culture.

3. Conclusion

Translation, especially literary translation, is inseparable from the cultural context. Only by closely integrating with the cultural context and absorbing different cultural connotations into different languages, the mutual integration between the source language and the target language can achieve expression without losing the color of the source language and clearly achieve the target goals. A translator makes good use of the interpretation of the cultural context and preserves it so that it is not only believable but also conveys the meaning correctly and finally polishes the text to make it elegant. Translation is not copying. The aesthetic need of the translator leaves a mark on the Translation beyond his control. If the writer artistically expresses his observations from life events in the language, the translator re-embodys the original text in a new language. For this, he needs to know the author's level of the reality mentioned in the work. Translation has a great influence on the development of the literature of every nation, because the history of translation is equal to the history of literature.

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